

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL CREATIVITY OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENT APPROACH.

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Abstract: In this article, the work carried out by the authors to improve their pedagogical skills and opportunities based on a competent approach in order to become quality and mature pedagogues in the future, as well as the shortcomings in these works, is the current problem, as well as the solution to this problem. proposals and comments aimed at.

Key words. Competent, physical education, pedagogue, expert, education, quality, profession, training, competence, ability, creativity, qualification, formation, development and method.

It is known that one of the necessary factors that ensure the free and independent practical activity of future pedagogues in professional activity is based on the formation of professional and pedagogical competence in them. The unique structure of pedagogical competence, the stages of its formation, and the development and implementation of effective mechanisms of using modern forms and methods of teaching in this process are of great importance.

In the modern world, the role of physical culture as a factor in the improvement of man and society is significantly increasing. Accordingly, society and its members pay sufficient attention to the quality and effectiveness of the training of specialists in the field of physical education, day by day to the level of professional qualifications. requirements are increasing. Turning to person-oriented education leads to the emergence of new goals of pedagogical education, including physical education. Based on the above, it is necessary to modernize the pedagogical personnel training system based on the introduction of new approaches and modern technologies to the educational field of the university.

In this regard, educational institutions play an important role in the system of training qualified pedagogues. The attention paid to the issues of education and upbringing in our republic, the importance of training pedagogues and increasing their professional competence is becoming more evident. At this point, if it is taken into account that the future pedagogue will act as the main subject in the organization of education at the important stages of the continuous education system in the future, the formation of their pedagogical competence and the achievement of efficiency in this regard are necessary measures.

Studying and analyzing the qualification requirements for the professional competence of pedagogues in all areas of continuing education, the following problems are evident in this regard:

- the disproportion between the modern requirements for the professional competence of pedagogues and the practical actions being taken to prepare educational institutions for professional activity;
- the fact that most graduates of pedagogical universities do not have the methodologically necessary preparation for organizing professional activities in educational institutions;
- modern pedagogical conditions for the formation of the professional competence of pedagogic specialists have not been established on the basis of a comprehensive system;

- lack of professional and innovative competence of teachers working in general education schools. The best way for us to solve these problems is to develop the professional competence of future physical education teachers.

A competent pedagogue - who is he? Questions arise, such as how the process of its formation takes place. In this context, it is important to define the meaning of the concept of "competence".

What is the concept of "competence": In the conditions of current market relations, being able to withstand strong competition, which has a priority in the labor market, requires every specialist to have professional competence and to increase it consistently. So what is competence? What qualities are reflected in the basis of professional competence? It is necessary for the teacher to be able to highlight the qualities of competence. In this place, we will talk about these and related ideas.

The English concept of "competence" literally means "ability". The content serves to illuminate "the effective use of theoretical knowledge in the activity, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional qualifications, skill and talent."

The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of the scientific research of psychologists. From a psychological point of view, competence is "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, engages in communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, consistently develops and ownership of a plan of action in complex processes.

Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level. Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work.

In the educational system based on the "competent" approach, the role of the teacher and the learner also changes. Because in the "knowledgeable" approach, the teacher is an active and main participant, while the learner is a passive receiver. In the "competent" approach, the learner becomes an active participant, because his educational activity is more focused on completing independent individual tasks and defending his results, constantly answering questions in creative practical exercises, and conducting individual research.

Analysis and results

The main place in the formation of competence is occupied by independent education of students. Because the future specialist is required not only to have knowledge and skills, but also to be able to apply them in practice. This can be achieved by teaching students to independently solve problematic assignments and tasks in the educational process. Based on this general goal, independent education accustoms future specialists to fully use their intellectual potential, to find the necessary knowledge, and to apply it in their practical activities in any conditions and situations. In a word, it prepares to work as a full-fledged, competitive specialist in social life and in the educational process.

During the student period, in cooperation with the teacher, relying on his advice, the skills and competencies of independent learning are formed. Learning materials specified in the curriculum, program and textbooks are mastered. It is taught to use in practical activities, to

achieve guaranteed results. In this process, paying attention to the independent activity of the student as much as possible will give a positive result. One of the useful aspects of independent education at a higher educational institution is that the student can find knowledge related to his profession and specialty outside of the curriculum and textbooks, and achieve further enrichment by conducting experimental tests. This, in turn, will encourage the formation of enterprising, creative and creative personnel.

Independent education creates positive competition among students. Learning from each other, they direct their mind, energy, and time to engage in useful activities. Unknown aspects of the student's talent are revealed by preparing for various competitions, participating in science olympiads and striving to win, participating in scientific and creative exhibitions. The student's self-confidence, intelligence and abilities increase. In particular, we will consider how these abilities of future pedagogues develop based on a competent approach. Knowledge - ability related to relevant fields of science (pedagogy, physical education, etc.). A teacher with this ability knows the subject not only in terms of volume, but in a wide and deep way, perfectly, he is interested in this subject, he also knows scientific research works.

The ability to receive explanations is the most important ability of a teacher. It is to be able to explain to the students in a comprehensible way, to be able to have an impact in general. It refers to students' mental state, interest, movement, experiences, situation, what they know or don't know, the causes that cause it, ways to eliminate it, tiredness, making it possible to rest and not hurrying, and being able to perform skills without mistakes in time and place. is caught.

The ability to observe is the ability to enter the inner world of the student. Such a teacher can quickly notice subtle changes in the student's psychology.

Speech ability is understood as the ability to express one's thoughts and feelings in a clear, clear, simple literary language (simplistically) in order to convey the purpose of one's education to students with the help of speech. It is extremely important to draw students' attention to which expressions, ideas, most important rules and directions in mastering the material taught by the teacher with their own words. The speech of the teacher is clear, vivid, impressive, the pronunciation is bright, expressive, emotional, it must not have stylistic and phonetic defects.

Organizational ability - firstly, the ability to organize a group of students, unite them, motivate them to perform their important tasks, guide them, and secondly, to plan their work (lessons, training, work) according to the purpose. It is very important to be able to use the most important time.

The ability to gain reputation is to have a direct emotional and volitional impact on students. His reputation is formed by his good knowledge of science, his ability to explain, his ability to motivate, his ability to punish (fairly), his kindness, understanding of the student, his behavior and hard work. His heart must be sincere, pure and honest. It would be correct to say that the effect of the teacher's treatment is determined by his respect for the personality of the student.

The ability to know in advance - the ability to foresee the consequences of one's own and the students' actions and activities, to know in advance, to know, that is, to be able to see pedagogically. For example, when two students quarrel, to determine which one is to blame, etc.

The ability to influence is the most important ability of a teacher. In order for him to have an impact, he needs to know his student and the state and heart of the student at that time. If the teacher cannot have an educational and educational effect on the student, all his efforts will be wasted. Let the teacher influence the student as much as possible in a positive way.

The conclusion is that the formation of competence of students of physical culture is the most effective way to become high-level specialists in the future. Competency development begins in a higher education institution and continues in the workplace under the supervision of experienced mentors. It should not be forgotten that high professional competence is not only the level of knowledge, but also practical skills, experience and personal qualities of the employee.

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